

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7979091

DERIVATIVE NAPHTOLS OF HIGHLY TOXIC NAPHTHALENE OXIDE AND PASSIVE SMOKER

Giorgi Parulava - Professor, Georgian State Teaching University of Physical Education and Sport, 49a, Ilia Chavchavadze Avenue, Tbilisi, Georgia;

giorgi.parulava@sportuni.ge .

David Zurabashvili - Professor, Tbilisi State University, 1 Ilia Chavchavadze Avenue, Tbilisi.

Murad Garuchava - Professor, Georgian State Teaching University of Physical Education and Sport, 49a, Ilia Chavchavadze Avenue, Tbilisi, Georgia;

murad.garuchava@sportuni.ge .

Elene Parulava - Master, Rhine-Waal University of Applied Sciences, 1, Marie-Curie-Straße, Kleve, Germany.

Aza Revishvili - Associate Professor, Georgian State Teaching University of Physical Education and Sport, 49a, Ilia Chavchavadze Avenue, Tbilisi, Georgia;

aza.revishvili@sportuni.ge .

Abstract. Research conducted by the authors in the scientific-research laboratory of the Tbilisi Center for Mental Health and Drug Addiction Prevention found that the smoke released as a result of burning tobacco contains not only naphthalene, but also its derivatives, namely: methyl, dimethyl and trimethylnaphthalenes. These substances do not exist in cigarettes themselves, but their formation in smoke is clearly related to terpene precursors, as well as thermal decomposition of isoprene polyolefins. In addition to the mentioned pyrolytic processes, photochemical reactions also play an important role. The presence of these highly toxic substances in a certain space carries a high risk in terms of the development of various diseases in humans. including cancer, coronary diseases, respiratory diseases, asthma attacks in passive smoking adolescents, etc.

Keywords: Highly toxic oxides, spectroscopic analysis, cigarette smoke, passive smoker, dizziness, quantitative analysis.

Introduction

Naphthalene is a solid crystalline substance with a characteristic odor. Insoluble in water, soluble in benzene, ether. Its chemical properties are very similar to benzene. It is easily nitrated, sulfonated, interacts with halogens. It differs from benzene in that it has even greater activity.

At high temperatures (the temperature of the distal part of the smoldering part of the cigarette reaches 800-1000°C during a deep puff), naphthalene hydroxy derivatives of naphthols are formed, which in their chemical properties are very close to benzene phenols ($C_{10}H_{8-n}(OH)_n$), where $n = 1, 2, 3$ and more. [1; 2; 16; 20]

Research goals

The main task of the paper is to find out how dangerous naphthalene, i.e. derivatives of highly toxic oxides, which are produced in cigarette smoke and are close to phenols of the benzene series, for the health of passive smokers, especially athletes.

Materials and Research Methods

The analysis was carried out by capillary chromatography on a PPF-Millipor-Waters chromatograph (USA). Integrator Data Modul730 (Waters). Program #4 - internal normalization. Capillary quartz column (WCOT, 120.0mx0.35mm). Stationary liquid phase OV-101. Coating thickness 5.0 microns. Dosing is pneumatic. The equilibrium of the gas phases was strictly observed. Loop volume 20.0 µl (Hamilton). The total retention value (100°C) for benzene is 2.800 ter. tar. Separation criteria 0.40. The modes were carried out using the "support method" (2.0% spread) in both the upper and lower ranges. Calibration standards (internal, by group affiliation) according to YSO, method A - "introduced-found". The analysis was repeated according to the "spot selection" 6 times for each ZONE with an interval of 10 days in order to clean the room. The results were processed on the basis of the SOSS computer program. Container (point, GOST-R-50021) air sampling (1.0 m³) was carried out in accordance with the design recommendations in accordance with GOST-30571, first before the start of the experiment (cleanliness of the air), and then at distances of 2.0 and 4.0 m from burning cigarette (from one pack, condensation according to GOST-5021) in a closed room with a volume of 36.0 m² (atmospheric conditions GOST-N-30571) after the second "PASS". A conventional laboratory smoking machine (GOST - 3308) was used, the puff resistance (GOSTISO-6565), the diameter of the cigarette (GOST-30041) was not taken into account. Measure the length of a filter, tip paper, cigarette butt, etc. were not carried out. GLC analysis was chosen as the most informative method for identifying multicomponent samples in the mode of high reproducibility and sensitivity. It corresponded to the level of "Reference - Private Class B" (Good Laboratory Practice for Trace OLP). [2; 3; 4; 5; 13]

Qualitative and quantitative studies of neutral volatile fractions of cigarette smoke not associated with methanol pyrolysis were carried out using gas chromatography methods. In the tobacco smoke of one completely smoked cigarette, the percentage of naphthalene with its individual derivatives was approximately: naphthalene 0.17; 1 and 2-methylnaphthalenes 0.5, 2.7 dimethylnaphthalenes - 0.26; 1.6 - dimethylnaphthalene - 1.3; 1,3,6 - trimethylnaphthalene 0.7. [2; 13; 17]

Spectroscopic analyzes in ultraviolet light also suggested the presence of 1.8-dimethylnaphthalene and acetonaphthalene in cigarette smoke. The formation of the above naphthalenes can be associated with both terpene precursors and thermal decomposition of isoprene polyfins. The presence of a significant amount of di and trimethylnaphthalenes in cigarette smoke makes the process of formation of polycyclic hydrocarbons in tobacco smoke understandable. [8; 9; 15; 16]

Preparative chromatography methods have also identified 1-naphthylamine and 2-naphthylamine in cigarette smoke. In cigarette smoke passed through a 3.5% hydrochloric acid solution, then filtered, diluted with water and extracted with ether, naphthylpentafluoro propionamides were isolated. [2; 13; 14]

Naphthalene and its derivatives contained in tobacco smoke penetrate the respiratory tract and the digestive tract (active and passive smoking). According to their toxicity, the compounds belong to the 4th hazard class (low-hazardous substances). [7; 10]

The negative processes occurring in the body of both active and passive smokers are reversible. Each person's sensitivity to naphthalene is not the same. Therefore, the clinical picture manifests itself with varying degrees of intensity. [11; 19]

Penetrating through the mucous membranes of the respiratory tract, naphthalene contained in cigarette smoke is quickly absorbed into the systemic circulation and has a toxic effect on the

central nervous system, causing headaches in the temples, parietal region, dizziness associated with brain damage. [12; 18]

Chronic poisoning with naphthalene (certain types and features of professional work) can cause a feeling of fatigue, decreased ability to work, fatigue and even drowsiness. Part of the naphthalene, which is absorbed through the intestines (the saliva of an active smoker), is excreted from the body in the form of naphthol, naphthoquinone, etc. At the same time, it is possible: inflammatory processes in the kidneys and bladder. In hot weather, when the air is heated above 35% °C, the chemical activity increases. [13; 20]

Results

Naphthalene is not found on its own in tobacco, wrapping paper, flavors, stabilizers, filters. Therefore, the analysis of its traces in tobacco smoke belongs to the category of substances "Introduced by man". Due to the high temperature (the temperature of the second puff can reach 800°C), highly toxic oxide derivatives of naphthols are formed in cigarette smoke, which in their properties are very close to benzene phenols. For the first time, only the presence of naphthalene was shown in cigarette smoke. Subsequently, di- and trimethylnaphthalenes were also identified in cigarette smoke by capillary chromatography. It is interesting to emphasize that propionamides were found in cigarette smoke in the form of pyrolysis products of naphthylpentafluoro. According to the regulation "On the composition of tobacco products and their packaging" (N302 of July 31, 2003, Georgia), one filter-containing cigarette must contain no more than 1.0 mg of nicotine, 10.0 mg of tar and 10.0 mg of carbon dioxide. However, the content of tobacco smoke components continues to be the subject of significant problems. This is due to the fact that the structure of tobacco smoke depends not only on the type and quality of the tobacco product or the nature of smoking, but also on environmental conditions (metabolic problems) at different distances (migration problems) from the "active" smoker. The effect of cigarette smoke on a "passive" smoker, the issues of volatility of individual components and, on the basis of this, the composition of tobacco smoke at different distances from an "active" smoker are almost not studied and require further research. Works have been published on the content of individual components (including tars) of tobacco smoke from Astra cigarettes (without a filter, Lagodekhi, Georgia) in the oral cavity (the first redoubt of contact) and their effect on the most important components of the supporting tissues of the teeth of heavy smokers. Studies have been carried out on the content of individual components of tobacco smoke at strictly fixed distances from the source and under different environmental conditions (risk problems). It is shown that the composition of tobacco smoke changes dramatically not only from the intensity of pyrolysis - the nature of the puff. It is extremely closely related to the characteristics (temperature, humidity, lighting) of the environment, which differentiate not only the composition of cigarette smoke, but also the nature of the volatility of each component of tobacco smoke in open and closed atmospheric conditions.

We carried out a quantitative analysis of naphthalene and some of its derivatives (methyl-dimethyltrimethyl naphthalenes) at distances of 2.0 and 4.0 m from an "active smoker" at an ambient temperature in the comfort zone of 18.0 - 20°C. The study is categorized as 'human trace amounts' in the 'interdestination range'. This choice is based on the fact that naphthalene is a toxic factor, and not a factor of individual sensitivity.

The table shows the average content of naphthalene and its methyl derivatives in 1.0 m² of air at a distance of 2.0 and 4.0 m from a burning cigarette.

The level of naphthalene and its methyl derivatives (ppm) at different distances from the cigarette in 180 seconds, after the second “pass”.

Our research has shown that after 180 sec. after the second puff, cigarette smoke at a distance of 2.0 m. from a burning cigarette contains naphthalene and its derivatives in the form of methyl-, dimethyl-, trimethylnaphthalenes. The level of dimethylnaphthalene (3.4-0.6 ppm) was the highest. It significantly exceeded the levels of naphthalene (2.7±0.4 ppm, $p < 0.001$), methylnaphthalene (1.2±0.07 ppm, $P < 0.001$) and trimethylnaphthalene (1.9±0.02 ppm, $p < 0.002$). At a distance of 4.0 m from the source in the indicated period of time, naphthalene and the above derivatives were also identified in cigarette smoke. The content of dimethylnaphthalene again turned out to be the highest. At a distance of 4.0 m from the source, after 180 sec. after the second puff, its level was equal to 4.9±0.7 ppm and significantly exceeded the level of naphthalene (2.6±0.5 ppm, $P < 0.001$). The level of methylnaphthalene did not exceed 1.1±0.08 ppm and was significantly lower than the level of naphthalene ($P < 0.001$). The content of trimethylnaphthalene in tobacco smoke at a distance of 4.0 m from a burning cigarette turned out to be higher than the level of methylnaphthalene (2.0±0.05 ppm, $P < 0.01$) and remained significantly lower than the level for Gugin ($P < 0.001$). Comparative analysis, according to fixed distances, showed that after 180 sec. after the second puff at distances of 2.0 and 4.0 from the burning cigarette, the level of naphthalene is almost the same. Accordingly, we have 2.7±0.4 ppm and 2.6±0.5 ppm ($P < 0.05$). With regard to methylnaphthalene, there were also no real changes according to the distance. At a distance of 2.0 m from a burning cigarette, the level of methylnaphthalene did not exceed 1.2 ± 0.07 ppm, while at a distance of 4.0 m it corresponded to 1.1 ± 0.08 ppm. The difference is not significant ($P > 0.05$). The level of dimethylnaphthalene increased significantly. After 180 sec. after the second puff, its level at a distance of 2.0 m from the source was 3.4 ± 0.6 ppm, while at a distance of 4.0 m from a burning cigarette it reached 4.9 ± 0.7 ppm. Variation-statistical analysis confirms the high significance of the increase ($P < 0.001$). The level of trimethylnaphthalene at both distances from the source turned out to be practically the same. At distances of 2.0 and 4.0 from a burning cigarette, it did not exceed 1.9 ± 0.02 ppm and 2.0-0.05 ppm, respectively. The difference is not significant ($P > 0.05$).

Conclusions

Thus, at distances of 2.0 m and 4.0 m from the source after 180 sec. after a second puff, cigarette smoke contains not only naphthalene, but also its following derivatives: methyl-, dimethyl- and trimethylnaphthalenes. Regardless of the distance, dimethylnaphthalenes are present in the greatest amount. They exceed the content not only of methyl and trimethyl derivatives of naphthalene, but also of naphthalene itself. It deserves special attention that the level of only dimethylnaphthalenes increases with distance from the source. At different distances from the source, the content of the remaining components does not change. According to modern concepts, the formation of naphthalene and its methyl derivatives in tobacco smoke (components that are not present on their own in a cigarette) is apparently associated with terpene precursors, as well as thermal decomposition of isoprene polyolefins. In addition to pyrolytic processes, photochemical reactions also play an important role. This is certainly consistent with the representation of a higher toxicity of "stale" cigarette smoke in an enclosed space compared to smoke from a freshly smoked cigarette.

The presence of the above-mentioned substances in a specific space is epidemiological and biochemical evidence of environmental pollution, which contributes to the presence of specific carcinogens in the blood and urine of non-smokers. Smoke inhalation causes lung cancer. The risk of developing coronary diseases increases by 30%. Naphthalene derivatives are a risk factor for platelet aggregation. Naphthalene derivatives have a significant effect on the respiratory system: production of large amounts of sputum, pain in the heart and chest area, reduction of lung capacity, asthma attacks. Passive smoking in adolescents causes an increase in asthma events by 40-60%.

Therefore, introducing a healthy way of life, getting rid of the harmful habit of smoking should become a bioethical norm, a moral requirement for every citizen.

References

1. Даулеткалиева Ж.А. Кулов Д.Б., Оценка степени ответственности граждан за свое здоровье с позиции медицинских работников. Проблемы социальной гигиены, здравоохранения и истории медицины. 2015;3: 11-14
2. Зурабашвили Д.З., Парулава Г.К., "Пассивный Курильщик", Вопросы медицины и спорта, Тбилиси, 2019. 295 ст.
3. Зурабашвили Д.З., Парулава Г.К., Гвишиани З.Н., Шанидзе Л.А., Гаричава М.В., Уровень содержания нафталина и его производных в табачном дыме. Медицинские новости Грузии. N1 (250) 2016:93-98.
4. Зурабашвили Д.З., Чантурия Н.Р., Капанадзе Л.Р., Хроматографический анализ отдельных токсических компонентов конденсата табачного дыма в биологических тканях. Мед. Новости Грузии. 2010;1(178):31-34
5. Зурабашвили Д.З., Парулава Г.К., Уровень никотина и котинина в волосах пассивных курильщиков. International Academy Journal. Web of Scholar.
6. Зурабашвили Д.З., Парулава Г.К., Уровень никотина и котинина в слюне пассивных курильщиков. International Academy Journal. Web of Scholar. 2(20), vol.1.February 2018:86-9
7. Криминалистическое исследование табачных изделий и их остатков. М. Мин. Юстиции и Судебной экспертизы. 2000;50

8. Савчук С.А., Веденин А.Н., Применение программы фиксации времени удерживания при хромато-масс-спектрометрическом определении анализируемых веществ. Российский химический журнал им Д.И.Менделеева. 2003, Т XLVII, N1, с.41
9. Савчук С.А., Родченков Г.М., Апполонова С.А., Никитина Н.М., Опыт практического применения новых ГК-МС методик в системе хи мико-токсикологических лабораторий и спортивном тестировании. Тезисы докладов Всероссийской конференции «Теория и практика хроматографии». Хроматография и нанотехнология. Самара. 6-9 июля 2009г. с. 58.
10. Cheng K-W, Glantz SA, Lightwood JM., Association between smokefree laws and voluntary smokefree-home rules. Am J Prev Med 2011;41(6):566-72
11. King BA, Dube SR, Tunan MA, Secondhand smoke exposure in cars among middle and high school students – United States, 2000-2009. Pediatrics 2012;129(3):446-52
12. Zhang X, Martinez-Donate AP, Kuo D, Jones NR., Palmersheim KA. Trends in home smoking bans in the USA, 1995-2007: prevalence, discrepancies and disparities. Tob Control 2012;21(3):330-6
13. Zurabashvili D., Parulava G., Gvishiani Z., Shanidze L., Garuchava M., The level of Naphthalene and its derivatives in Tobacco Smoke, Georgian Medical News, 2011;1(250):93-97
14. Ellis J.A., Gwynn C., Grag R., Philburn R end.al., Secondhand smoke exposure among nonsmokers nationally and in New York City. Nicotine Tob.Res. 2009,11:362-370
15. Wall M.A., Johnson J., Jacob P., and Benowitz N.L., Cotinine in the serum, saliva nad urine of nonsmokers, passive smokers and active smokers Am. J. Pub. Health 1988,788:699-701
16. <https://ka.worldlifeadvice.com/10768125-what-is-naphthalene>
17. <https://www.medalpha.ge/blogi/tambaqos-mavneoba.html> - Harmfulness of Tobacco
18. <http://www.allmedic.ge/samedicino-blogi/136/sigareti-da-janmrTeloba/> - Cigarette and Health
19. <https://russian7.ru/post/chem-opasen-naftalin/> - Why is it Illegal
20. https://www.ilo.org/dyn/icsc/showcard.display?p_lang=ru&p_card_id=0667&p_version=2 - Tables